

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Orjingene**FIRST NAME:** Obinna**PROGRAM CODE:** PHGH**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied U.S. U.K. conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: Microsoft Word 365 on Windows 10

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP) (samples below):

1. The Basics of Essay Writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-6)
3. Style Guide (EUCLID 2019, 25-26)
4. Latin Expressions and Abbreviations (EUCLID 2019, 56-61)
5. American Versus British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-35)
6. Chicago Manual of Style (EUCLID 2019, 49-55)
7. Quotation Marks (EUCLID 2019, 6-7)

UNDERSTANDING THE BASIC OF ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

I grew up in a community with a diverse socio-cultural background. Fortunately for me, English language has been the official language of learning, from my high school up to my postgraduate program. Professionally, I also have consistently communicated in English, but I clearly understood the significance and the need for continuous learning especially in the pursue of a doctorate program. Hence, the need for me to fully understand the basic of academic essay writing became very pertinent, and I am glad EUCLID ACA-401D period one has provided me such a platform to understand and apply these basics. The 14 minutes' study video tried to summarize a detail approach to response paper, citations, the use of English, quotation mark and generally the rule of style. I believe, these will be vital for a successful completion of this program, especially in subsequent response paper, quiz development (EUCLID 2019, 1) and I hope to apply same professionally.

2) THE BASIC OF ESSAY WRITING

Chapter one of the ACA-401D coursepack for period one (1) provided the fundamentals of academic essay writing, and I understood better, the need for a thesis statement, more like, thinking through what a problem statement or study question will be structured into and providing critical discussions with examples, with the aid of credible academic sources that are properly referenced (ibid.). The importance of developing a draft essay for further review cannot be overemphasized, as noted in the coursepack, this provide the opportunity to make necessary corrections and inputs as may be applicable, and over the years, I found this very useful when preparing presentations and briefs for seminars and conferences.

It is also important to consider peer-reviewed studies and evidenced based papers, as this helps to broaden the writer's perspectives on the subject of study, and as noted in the ACA-401D coursepack, "essay writing requires both creative and critical thinking" (EUCLID 2019, 2). Globally, for academic essays to be acceptable and acknowledged, to be objective in academic essay writing, it is paramount, that there is a clear separation between facts and fallacies, and from experience, I always tried to make a note of relevant information, their sources and bibliographic details, this help not only my view point, but also in establishing other contrasting ideas based on facts. Evaluating differing arguments may not necessarily expand the scope of your paper, but make it more inclusive and robust for a wider audience. The quality of any research or study depend on the amount of evidence and facts it contains, and this makes our writing more robust.

When writing an academic essay, it is important to present a well-structured argument that is self-explanatory. This applies in the current context of Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19), scientists are using evidence based analysis in the development of the COVID vaccines, ongoing clinical trials and public health preventions are all based on evidence and facts from prior pandemics and learnings as documented in researches and peer-reviewed journals (Khuroo et al. 2020, 1). As a health specialist working in a multi-sectoral agency, I rely on evidenced based data to make informed decision on health programming both at the national and sub-national level, it is easier to advocate for resources and funding for health programs when the context is supported by facts. And it is important to critically analysis and draw conclusion from such evidence (EUCLID 2019, 3).

Referencing of source materials is key in academic essay writing, this shows that credit is given to authors of studies or papers used in developing your thoughts. And as noted in the ACA-401D coursepack, "referencing guides as plagiarism" (EUCLID 2019, 4). In the work we do, in trying to showcase visibility to interventions and programs, photo credits are usually given not just for patency sake, but this ensures that the work we do are properly documented and can be credibly shared and scaled up in places of interest.

3) THE ACT OF PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism as defined by the ACA-401D coursepack, is “when the writer uses a source of information without giving credits to the author of that source of information” (EUCLID 2019, 5). Oxford English dictionary in 1921 included the word plagiarism, the committee on publication ethics in 1999 defined plagiarism as “the unreferenced use of others’ published and unpublished ideas including research grant applications to submission under new authorship of a complex paper, sometimes in a different language. It may occur at any stage of planning, research, writing or publication; it applies to print and electronic versions” (Handa 2008, 301-3).

In my daily routine, it often easy to copy and paste shared information on social media platforms such as WhatsApp, Facebook et cetera without necessarily crediting the original owner or verifying the source of such information. But with my understanding from the ACA-401D coursepack, it is important to credit any information that is borrowed from another source (EUCLID 2019, 5), as this gives credence to the original author of the work. And as mentioned in the course material, these can be achieved through proper referencing and in text citation.

Paraphrasing is one aspect of academic writing that is better understood over time, I personally paraphrase ideas and sourced information from peer-reviewed journals and also reference them appropriately, even though this may be confusing and sometimes tempting, since it is believed that those words are being put in your own words, one might be tempted not to reference. But as rightly pointed out by both the Euclid University orientation course (EUCLID 2020, 2) and the ACA-401D coursepack (EUCLID 2019, 5, 16), strict compliance to copyright regulation is expected by every student. I personally take this guidance as a code of conduct as would be applied by any organizational policy elsewhere, therefore the need to adhere and abide by Euclid University policy.

4) THE RULE OF STYLES GUIDE

Style guide as defined by (EUCLID 2019, 24) is “a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent”. I understood that there are different styles guide available, and these includes the economist style guide, the BBC News style guide, the Chicago Manual of style and the World Health Organization (WHO) style guide. Euclid University prefers student to use the Turabian rule of style, except where otherwise stated (EUCLID 2019, 2), and Turabian rule of style is aligned with the recently published Chicago Manual of Style 17th edition.

Although, the Chicago Manual of Style (CMS) crib sheet contents (version 2003) has been revised, yet the content remains relevant. I was used to using the abbreviated forms of et cetera and id est, but this has changed with my understanding of the ACA-401D coursepack and going forward will help improve my competency and writing skills. Same applies in the use of italics and quotation mark in some exception, as italics are used for emphasis in academic writing (EUCLID 2019, 45), quotation marks are also used to

enclose translation of non-English terms within the text of academic write up. Another interesting aspect for the CMS is the date format, prior to this time, I was used to the universal or European format of, Day, Month and Year, but with the revised CMS the American format of month, date and year is now the recommended standard (EUCLID 2019, 46).

Overall, I understand better, how rule of style applies to different aspect of academic essay writing, from the paper layout, the use of font, structure and the use of headings et cetera. The application of these rules will play a critical role in the consistency of my academic essay writing going forward.

5) AMERICAN AND THE BRITISH ENGLISH LANGUAGE FORMAT

In the year 2018, I had the opportunity to undertake a course in the United States of America, this was my first classroom exposure to the use of the American English language format, which somewhat differed from what I was used to at the time. And globally, as rightly mentioned by (EUCLID 2019, 27), American English has a more dominant influence, not necessarily because of its standards and attributes, but an array of factors plays a critical role in influencing this, these include, the socio-economics and political influence of the American States across the globe. Most interestingly is the fact that they share a lot of similarities, and in some cases, the American and British English share the same spelling but are pronounced differently. The word “laboratory” is spelled as laboratory for both versions of English but differ in pronunciation.

Another significant uniqueness in both the American and the British English is periods, commas and quotation marks (EUCLID 2019, 35)

In most cases, I am already used to the British English, since the Nigerian history is of the British descent and this explains why the British English language format was used in my peer-reviewed journals; *Global Disease Outbreak and Effect on Maternal, Newborn, and Child Health, and Effectiveness of Community based intervention in reducing Maternal Mortality in Sub Saharan Africa*, work flow, presentations et cetera. Suffice to say, that the importance and adherence to the use of the American English as recommended by Euclid University cannot be overemphasized.

6) CONCLUSION

The ACA-401D period one (1) coursepack provided me with the requisite tools I will need to go through the International Academic Writing course, and the very detailed and summarized study video by Prof. Laurent Cleenewerck gave an overview on response paper format and general rule of style, which in both cases can be referenced easily.

Going through the entire course pack, had provided me with a better understanding and clarity especially in grey areas which prior to this time was obscured. Going forward, I plan to put to practice this newly acquired knowledge in future academic writing and I hope to be able to apply same in subsequent periods and courses for the PHGH program, and also to reflect these refinements in learning with professional colleagues. As such, I must commend the effort put in by my tutors in revising the ACA-401D coursepack and making it very user friendly and a fundamental tool for fresh postgraduate students like myself.

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